

INDIAN TRAFFIC SIGN DETECTION AND RECOGNITION USING DEEP CONVOLUTION NEURAL NETWORK

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Abstract : Road and traffic sign recognition is an important field of study. It has got its importance in the areas like the development of intelligent transport system (ITS) and road safety norms. It can help the driver to inform about the upcoming signs that can help to navigate and to avoid potential risky traffic violations and situations. Many different techniques were available in the literature that are predominantly based on Hog and SIFT features. In this paper, we propose to use Deep Convolution Neural Networks to build a model that can predict the type of traffic sign. The database of traffic sign is taken from Kaggle website. The implementation is done by using 24 classes. The results are tested for Indian traffic signs and the results are produced with better accuracy.

IndexTerms – Convolution neural network, Traffic sign recognition, training and testing data.

I.INTRODUCTION

Road and traffic signs are designed for the purpose to regulate and guide the road users. They help in providing safety both for vehicular and pedestrians [1]. A lot of attention is being given to follow the traffic rules while driving manually and also being implemented in self-driving vehicles. The introduction of intelligent traffic system enabled the development of various technologies related to transportation. One of them is the traffic sign identification and recognition. To achieve safe driving, it is necessary to recognize the traffic signs. The position of a traffic sign in city limits will be usually in the amidst of other boards, people movement and other constraints. Visually it can be identified by a person, but not so easily by the machine. The challenges involve the identification of presence of a traffic sign and further analysis of it for recognition.

Traffic signs are characterized by a number of features that can be recognized in all environments. Some of the features involves;

- They are 2-D shapes printed on a metal plate with reflecting paints
- Their colors are fixed
- Each symbol is unique. The pattern and size of write up is always fixed with respect to font size and type.

A traffic sign recognition usually will have two phases, detection and classification. The detection phase reads the images with traffic sign and the classification determines the traffic sign category. The information of traffic signs usually involves color, symbols and shape. The Fig. 1 shows some of the examples of Indian traffic signs.

Figure. 1: Sample representation of Indian traffic sign

Literature indicates several methods used to identify the traffic signs. A major research was done by [1] using a mixture pattern recognition and computer vision problems and was able to achieve 88% accuracy. As a pattern recognition part, support vector machine (SVM) was used. Some of the methods used color-based methods to perform the detection [2,3,4]. Many researchers made use of HSV and HIS color space also [5,6]. They made use of different image sizes for recognition. Traffic signs are usually will have specific geometric shapes. This can be utilized along with texture and color features. Some of the authors who used shape-based methods involved the abilities of Sobel, Prewitt, canny edge detection and Hough transform methods to detect shapes [7,8]. The main problem with color based methods is that, the color is not same on all weather conditions. The outdoor scenarios will always keep changing. Also, the method was not real time and time consuming. Few authors utilized the Histogram Oriented Gradients (HOG) along with SVM and adaboost classifiers. They posed the problem with its real time implementation. Machine learning based methods are getting more popular now a days. Authors incorporated Neural networks, Random forests for classification and detection process [9,10]. The results were inspiring. The work was taken further by using deep learning methods [11]. Other methods like Yolo and single-shot detectors (SSD) framework based methods found to be promising in detecting traffic sign [12]. A detailed view on traffic sign classification is listed in [13] and it provides the details with achieved accuracy of various methods. In spite of so many works accomplished, still there is a room for improvement.

In this paper, an attempt is made to address the issue of detecting and recognizing a large number of Indian traffic-sign categories suitable for automating traffic-sign inventory management using Deep Convolution Neural Network (CNN).

II. IMPLEMENTATION

The implementation uses pre-processing, Feature extraction, Training & testing, Sign recognition accuracy with necessary modelling feedback. The Fig. 2 Shows the implementation steps.

Figure 2: Block diagram of implementation process.

The dataset of Indian traffic sign is considered. The image data set is taken from Kaggle website. The images with RGB having different size are resized to 64*64 dimension. The dataset is then divided into training, testing and validation set. The hold-out cross validation technique splits the data into three mutually independent sets. A total of 24 classes is used for each image and are named in Arabic and stored in a folder.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

For implementation, a total of 83 training and 83 testing images are considered. First the images are trained for better accuracy. The number of epoch are increased until we obtain almost stagnant change in accuracy. Then the testing face is started. Fig. 3 shows the details of data simulation window indicating the training and testing images. Fig. 4 shows the graph of training and validation model accuracy against the epoch. The system is trained for such 83 traffic signs. The identification of the traffic sign also depends on the quality of input image. The system is trained to detect good quality images and slightly rotated images. Image with distortion and identification of multiple images in one window is not trained. Also, distortion due to weather conditions is not considered in this paper. For all trained cases, we are able to achieve close to 98% accuracy.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this research, an attempt is made for automatic identification of traffic sign by using standard data base. Deep convolution neural network frame work is used for the implementation. The results indicate that, the proposed method performs better in identifying the traffic signs with better accuracy. Further, it is intended to extend it for real time video and also to detect multiple signs in single frame of video.

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Python 3.7.0 Shell
File Edit Shell Debug Options Window Help
Python 3.7.0 (v3.7.0:1bf9cc5093, Jun 27 2018, 04:59:51) [MSC v.1914 64 bit (AMD64)] on win32
Type "copyright", "credits" or "license()" for more information.
>>>
RESTART: C:\Users\lenovo\AppData\Local\Programs\Python\Python37\ALL PROGRAMS\Traffic sign CODE\main_trainng.py
Using TensorFlow backend.
['10', '11', '12', '13', '14', '15', '16', '17', '18', '19', '1', '20', '21', '22', '23', '24', '25', '26', '27', '28', '29', '2', '30', '31', '32', '33', '34', '35', '36', '37', '38', '39', '3', '40', '41', '42', '43', '44', '45', '46', '47', '48', '49', '4', '50', '51', '52', '53', '54', '55', '56', '57', '58', '59', '5', '60', '61', '62', '63', '64', '65', '66', '67', '68', '69', '6', '70', '71', '72', '73', '74', '75', '76', '77', '78', '79', '7', '80', '81', '82', '83', '8', '9']
There are 83 total categories.
['10', '11', '12', '13', '14', '15', '16', '17', '18', '19', '1', '20', '21', '22', '23', '24', '25', '26', '27', '28', '29', '2', '30', '31', '32', '33', '34', '35', '36', '37', '38', '39', '3', '40', '41', '42', '43', '44', '45', '46', '47', '48', '49', '4', '50', '51', '52', '53', '54', '55', '56', '57', '58', '59', '5', '60', '61', '62', '63', '64', '65', '66', '67', '68', '69', '6', '70', '71', '72', '73', '74', '75', '76', '77', '78', '79', '7', '80', '81', '82', '83', '8', '9']
There are 166 total burn images.

There are 83 training images.
There are 83 test images.
  
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Figure 3: Simulation window showing training and testing numbers

Figure 4: Graph indicating the training and validation

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